

Accelerated Testing for Long Term-Durability of Advanced CFRP Laminates for Marine Use

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SUMMARY: The prediction of long-term fatigue life of advanced CFRP laminates for marine use under temperature and water environments were performed by our developed accelerated testing methodology based on the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP). Three kinds of CFRP laminates employed were conventional plain fabric T300 carbon fibers/vinylester, flat yarn plain fabric T700 carbon fibers/vinylester and multi-axial knitted T700 carbon fibers/vinylester for marine use. These CFRP laminates were prepared under three water absorption conditions of Dry, Wet and Wet+Dry after molding. The three-point bending constant strain rate (CSR) tests for three kinds of CFRP laminates at three conditions of water absorption were carried out at various temperatures and strain rates. Furthermore, the three-point bending fatigue tests for these specimens were carried out at various temperatures and frequencies. As the results, the flexural CSR and fatigue strengths of these CFRP laminates strongly depends on water absorption as well as time and temperature. The master curves of fatigue strength as well as CSR strength for these CFRP laminates at these conditions are constructed by using the test data based on TTSP. It is possible to predict the long term fatigue life for these CFRP laminates under an arbitrary temperature and water absorption conditions by using the master curves. Additionally, the time- temperature- water absorption superposition principle (TTWSP) holds for the flexural CSR and fatigue strengths for these CFRP laminates.

KEYWORD: Durability, Fatigue, Accelerated testing, CFRP laminates, Temperature, Moisture

INTRODUCTION

Recently carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) has been used for the primary structures of airplanes, ships, spacecrafts and others, in which the high reliability should be kept during the long-term operation. Therefore, it is strongly expected that the accelerated testing methodology for the long-term life prediction of composite structures exposed under the actual environments of temperature, water, and others is established.

The mechanical behavior of polymer resins exhibits time and temperature dependence, called viscoelastic behavior, not only above the glass transition temperature T_g but also below T_g [1-8]. Furthermore, the viscoelastic behavior of polymer resins also depends on the water absorption [9-12]. Thus, it can be presumed that the mechanical behavior of polymer composites significantly depends on the water absorption as well as time and temperature.

This paper is concerned with the prediction of long-term fatigue life of advanced CFRP

laminates for marine use under temperature and water environments. Three kinds of CFRP laminates employed were conventional plain fabric T300 carbon fibers/vinylester, flat yarn plain fabric T700 carbon fibers/vinylester and multi-axial knitted T700 carbon fibers/vinylester for marine use. These CFRP laminates were prepared under three water absorption conditions of Dry, Wet and Wet+Dry after molding. The three-point bending constant strain rate (CSR) tests for three kinds of CFRP laminates at three conditions of water absorption were carried out at various temperatures and strain rates. Furthermore, the three-point bending fatigue tests for these specimens were carried out at various temperatures and frequencies. The time, temperature, and water absorption dependencies of flexural fatigue strength as well as flexural CSR strength for these CFRP laminates are discussed based on the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP) and time- temperature- water absorption superposition principle (TTWSP).

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Preparation of Specimens

Three kinds of CFRP laminates employed were conventional plain fabric T300 carbon fibers/vinylester (T300/VE), flat yarn plain fabric T700 carbon fibers/vinylester (T700/VE:F) and multi-axial knitted T700 carbon fibers/vinylester (T700/VE:K) for marine use. These CFRP laminates were formed by resin transfer molding (RTM). All of CFRP laminates was cured at room temperature over 24 hours. The fiber volume fraction was approximately 51%. The thickness of the laminates was 2mm.

These CFRP laminates were prepared under three water absorption conditions of Dry, Wet and Wet+Dry after molding. Dry specimens by holding the cured specimens at 150°C for 2 hours in air, Wet specimens by soaking Dry specimens in hot water of 95°C for 120 hours and Wet+Dry specimens by dehydrating the Wet specimens at 150°C for 2 hours in air were respectively prepared as shown in Table 1. The water contents of Dry and Wet+Dry specimens were 0% and that of Wet specimen was 0.6%.

Table 1: Preparing conditions for Dry, Wet, and Wet+Dry specimens

	Water content	In air	In water	In air
Dry	0%	150°C x 2h	-	-
Wet	0.6%	150°C x 2h	+ 95°C x 120h	-
Wet+Dry	0%	150°C x 2h	+ 95°C x 120h	+ 150°C x 2h

Experimental Procedures

To evaluate the viscoelastic behavior of matrix vinylester (VE) resin, the three-point bending creep tests for the neat vinylester resin prepared at Dry, Wet and Wet+Dry conditions were carried out under various temperatures using a creep testing machine with temperature chamber. The creep compliance D_c was calculated from the deflection δ at the center of specimen using the following equation:

$$D_c = \frac{4bh^3\delta}{P_0L^3} \quad (1)$$

where P_0 is the applied constant load (58.8N), L is the span (50mm), and b and h are the width

(25mm) and the thickness (3.0mm) of specimen, respectively.

The three-point bending CSR tests for three kinds of CFRP laminates at Dry, Wet and Wet+Dry conditions were carried out at various temperatures and strain rates. The span is $L=60\text{mm}$, and the width and thickness are $b=15\text{mm}$ and $h=2.0\text{mm}$, respectively. The CSR tests were conducted at three loading-rates $V=0.02, 2, 200 \text{ mm/min}$ and various constant temperatures T using an universal testing machine with temperature chamber. The flexural CSR strength σ_s is calculated from the maximum load P_s by

$$\sigma_s = \frac{3P_s L}{2bh^2} \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, the three-point bending fatigue tests for these specimens were carried out at various constant temperatures T and two loading frequencies $f=2\text{Hz}$ and 0.02Hz using an electro-hydraulic servo testing machine with temperature chamber. The stress ratio R (= minimum stress/maximum stress) was 0.05. The length, width, thickness of specimen, and span are the same to those for the flexural CSR tests. The flexural fatigue strength σ_f is defined by maximum applied load P_{\max} for the number of cycles to failure N_f .

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3P_{\max} L}{2bh^2} \quad (3)$$

In order to prevent the dryness of specimens at Wet condition during creep, CSR, and fatigue tests, the specimens were wrapped by a vinyl bag with including distilled water in the bag.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Creep Compliance

The left side of Fig.1 shows the creep compliance D_c versus testing time t at various temperatures T for Dry, Wet and Wet+Dry specimens of VE resin. The master curves of D_c versus the reduced time t' were constructed by shifting D_c at various constant temperatures along the log scale of t and the log scale of D_c . Since the smooth master curve of D_c for each specimen can be obtained as shown in the right side of each graph, the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP) is applicable for each D_c . From Fig.1 (b) and (c), it is cleared that D_c increases with water absorption and returns perfectly to that of Dry specimen by re-drying after water absorption.

The horizontal time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_0}(T)$ and the vertical temperature shift factor $b_{T_0}(T)$ at a reference temperature T_0 plotted in Fig.2 are respectively defined by

$$\log a_{T_0}(T) = \log t - \log t' \quad (4)$$

$$\log b_{T_0}(T) = \log D_c(t, T) - \log D_c(t', T_0) \quad (5)$$

The upper side of Fig.3 shows the master curves of D_c for Dry and Wet specimens of VE resin. The grand-master curve for D_c versus the reduced-reduced time t'' can be constructed by shifting the master curve D_c for Wet specimen along the log scale of t' and the log scale of D_c so that they overlap on D_c at the reference water content $W_0=0\%$ (Dry specimen) to form a single smooth grand-master curve as shown in the bottom side of this figure. Therefore, the TTWSP is applicable for D_c .

The time-temperature-water absorption shift factor $a_{T_0, W_0}(T, W)$ and temperature-water absorption shift factor $b_{T_0, W_0}(T, W)$ at a reference water content W_0 plotted in Fig.4 are respectively defined by

$$\log a_{T_0, W_0}(T, W) = \log t - \log t'' \quad (6)$$

$$\log b_{T_0, W_0}(T, W) = \log D_c(t, T, W) - \log D_c(t'', T_0, W_0) \quad (7)$$

Fig.1: Master curves of creep compliance for VE resin

Fig.2: Time-temperature shift factors and temperature shift factors of creep compliance for VE resin

Fig.3: Grand-master curve of creep compliance for VE resin

(a) Time-temperature-water absorption shift factor $a_{T_0, W_0}(T, W)$

(b) Temperature-water absorption shift factor $b_{T_0, W_0}(T, W)$

Fig.4: Shift factors of creep compliance for VE resin

Flexural CSR strength

The left side of each graph in Fig.5 shows the flexural CSR strength σ_s versus time to failure t_s at various temperatures T for Dry, Wet, Wet+Dry specimens of T300/VE and T700/VE:F, where t_s is the time period from initial loading to maximum load during testing. The master curves of σ_s versus the reduced time to failure t_s' were constructed by shifting σ_s at various constant temperatures along the log scale of t_s and the log scale of σ_s using the same $a_{T_0}(T)$ and a half of $b_{T_0}(T)$ for D_c of VE resin shown in Fig.2. Since the smooth master curve of σ_s for each specimen can be obtained as shown in the right side of each graph, the TTSP for D_c of VE resin is also applicable for each σ_s . It is cleared from Fig.5 that σ_s for T300/VE and T700/VE:F decreases with water absorption and returns to that of Dry specimen by re-drying after water absorption. The same results was obtained to σ_s for T700/VE:K.

Figure 6 shows the master curves of σ_s for Dry and Wet specimens of T300/VE, T700/VE:F, and T700/VE:K. The grand-master curves of σ_s are obtained by shifting the master curve of σ_s for Wet specimen along the log scale of t_s' and the log scale of D_c using the same $a_{T_0, W_0}(T, W)$ and a half of $b_{T_0, W_0}(T, W)$ for D_c of VE resin shown in Fig.4. The grand-master curves of normalized σ_s for T300/VE, T700/VE:F, and T700/VE:K were constructed as shown in Fig.7. Therefore, the TTWSP is applicable for σ_s of these CFRP laminates. It is cleared from this graph that the degradation rate of flexural CSR strength is determined only by increasing of time, temperature and water absorption and is independent upon fiber constitutions which are the type, volume fraction and weaves.

The fracture mode for these CFRP laminates is the compressive fracture of warp carbon fibers in the compression side of specimen for all condition tested. In this case, the slope of relation between $\log \sigma_s$ of CFRP laminates and $\log D_c$ of matrix VE is -1/2 based on Dow's theory [13]. Therefore, we considered that the vertical shift amount for σ_s is a half of that for D_c as mentioned above.

Fig.5: Master curves of flexural CSR strength for T300/VE and T700/VE:F

Fig.6: Master curves of flexural CSR strength for Dry and Wet specimens of T300/VE, T700/VE:F, and T700/VE:K

Fig.7: Grand master curves of normalized flexural CSR strength for T300/VE, T700/VE:F, and T700/VE:K

Flexural fatigue strength

To describe the master curve of flexural fatigue strength σ_f , we need the reduced frequency f' in addition to the reduced time to failure t_f' , each defined by

$$f' = f \cdot a_{T_0}(T) \quad , \quad t_f' = \frac{t_f}{a_{T_0}(T)} = \frac{N_f}{f'} \quad (8)$$

where N_f is the number of cycles to failure.

The σ_f versus N_f at frequency $f=2\text{Hz}$ for Dry and Wet specimens of T300/VE and T700/VE:F are shown in Fig.8 where σ_f at $N_f=1/2$ is represented by σ_s at $t_s=(2f)^{-1}$. On the upper figure of each graph in Fig.9, σ_f versus t_f' curves for several f' at T_0 are depicted by solid lines, which are obtained by converting N_f on Fig.8 into t_f' using Eq.(8), the time-temperature shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ and temperature shift factors $b_{T_0}(T)$ of CSR strength for each specimen. The master curves of σ_f for fixed N_f indicated by solid lines in the lower figure are constructed by connecting the points of the same N_f on the curves of each f' indicated by dotted lines in this figure.

In order to confirm the applicability of TTSP for fatigue strength, we predicted the σ_f - N_f curves at $f=0.02\text{Hz}$ and compared them with the test results as shown in Fig.10. The predicted σ_f from fatigue master curves agree well with experimental ones, therefore, the TTSP for CSR strength also holds for fatigue strength.

The upper figure of each graph in Fig.11 shows the master curves of σ_f at $N_f=1/2$ and 10^5 for Dry and Wet specimens of T300/VE and T700/VE:F. These master curves can be superimposed by shifting the master curves for Wet specimen along the log scale of t_f' and log scale of σ_f using the same time-temperature-water absorption shift factor $a_{T_0, W_0}(T, W)$ and the temperature-water absorption shift factor $b_{T_0, W_0}(T, W)$ for CSR strength of each CFRP laminates as shown in the bottom figure in Fig.11. Therefore, the TTWSP also holds for σ_f of T300/VE and T700/VE:F.

Fig.8: Flexural fatigue strength versus number of cycles to failure for frequency $f= 2\text{Hz}$ for T300/VE and T700/VE:F

(a) Dry specimen for T300/VE

(c) Dry specimen for T700/VE:F

(b) Wet specimen for T300/VE

(d) Wet specimen for T700/VE:F

Fig. 9: Master curves of flexural fatigue strength for T300/VE and T700/VE:F

(a) Dry specimen for T300/VE

(c) Dry specimen for T700/VE:F

(b) Wet specimen for T300/VE

(d) Wet specimen for T700/VE:F

Fig.10: Flexural fatigue strength versus number of cycles to failure for frequency $f=0.02\text{Hz}$ for T300/VE and T700/VE:F

(a) T300/VE

(b) T700/VE:F

Fig.11: Grand master curves of flexural fatigue strength for T300/VE and T700/VE:F

Figure 12 shows the master curves of normalized σ_f for Dry and Wet specimens of T300/VE and T700/VE:F. It is cleared that the σ_f of both laminates strongly decreases with time to failure, temperature and water absorption, however decreases scarcely with N_f .

Fig.12: Normalized flexural fatigue strength for T300/VE and T700/VE:F

CONCLUSION

The prediction of long-term fatigue life of advanced CFRP laminates for marine use under temperature and water environments were performed by our developed accelerated testing methodology based on the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP). The three-point bending CSR and fatigue tests for three kinds of CFRP laminates at three conditions of water absorption were carried out at various temperatures and loading rates. As the results, the flexural fatigue strength of these CFRP laminates strongly depends on water absorption as well as time and temperature, however scarcely depends on the number of cycles to failure. The master curves of fatigue strength for these CFRP laminates are constructed by using the test data based on TTSP. It is possible to predict the long term fatigue life for these CFRP laminates under an arbitrary temperature and water absorption conditions by using the master curves. Additionally, the time- temperature- water absorption superposition principle (TTWSP) holds for the flexural fatigue strengths as well as the flexural CSR strengths for these CFRP laminates. Furthermore, the degradation rate of fatigue strength of these CFRP laminates is determined only by increasing of time, temperature and water absorption and is independent upon fiber constitutions which are the type, volume fraction and weaves.

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